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TERMINOLOGIZATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE

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Key words: *phrase, phraseology, phraseological units, term, terminology, terminologization, structure, semantics, scientific text, discourse, scientific discourse.*

In the modern linguistic area, special attention is paid to the study of phraseological units and their use in scientific discourse. Phraseology, as a branch of linguistics, studies stable expressions that have a specific meaning and cannot be disassembled into their component parts without loss of meaning. Terminology of phraseological units is one of the current areas of research in this area.

The study of terminology of phraseological units in scientific discourse is relevant and important, as it allows us to expand our understanding of the use of phraseology in the scientific field. Scientific discourse requires accuracy and clarity in the expression of thoughts, and research into the terminology of phraseological units will help improve communication and avoid misunderstandings. In addition, studying this topic will provide a better understanding of the processes of language development and changes in scientific society.

It is known that in the 60s of the 20th century, many new terms appeared in the language due to the rapid growth of scientific knowledge. Therefore, the terminological phenomenon has attracted the attention of many linguists and researchers. "Such a sharp change in the development of terminology was connected with the fact that it began to be considered as a special, rapidly developing lexical system, a composition of the national vocabulary existing according to a certain pattern" [Алексеева 2003: 37-38].

In the 70-80s of the last century the problems of terminology in world linguistics have been studied extensively by V.M. Leychik, K.Ya. Averbukh, I.N. Volkova, A.S. Gerd, A.I. Moiseev, E.F. Skorokhod'ko and

other scientists [9]. In particular: 1) linguistic description and organization of the essence of the term; 2) automated methods of terminological analysis; 3) analysis of terms in order to create languages for modern information systems; 4) standardization of scientific and technical terminology. The term has united and continues to unite all these fields to this day.

The problems of the impact of terminology on the formation of phraseological units are widely covered in the works of F.P. Filin, F.P. Sorokoletov, V.G. Gak, Yu.S. Sorokin [Филин 1981; Сороколетов 1981; Гак 1998; Сорокин 1972] and other scientists. For example, F.P. Filin, talking about special terminology, noted that "a widely used literary language is the most important source of vocabulary expansion" [Филин 1981: 183].

In order to achieve the goal set in this research work and fulfill the set of tasks, based on the problem of terminologization of phraseological units in contemporary linguistics, a multi-faceted interdisciplinary approach was used to study and describe these units, and the following linguistic and interdisciplinary research methods were used: linguistic description method (terminology in the description and analysis of phraseological units as an object of terminologization); the method of oppositions (terminologization of phraseological units); methods of communicative linguistics, in particular, the transformational method (in the analysis of structural or semantic changes of terminologization of phraseological units depending on the situation); semantic method

(in determining the meaning of phraseological units).

Phraseological units are considered one of the important components of the language, play an important role in communication, enrich the speech and facilitate the delivery of certain semantic content. According to E.N. Dimitrieva, phraseological units can undergo changes and go through terminologization and reterminologization processes. According to the scientist: “Terminologization is the process of phraseological units acquiring a special terminological meaning within a certain field of knowledge or activity” [Димитриева 2010]. Indeed, language is constantly developing, undergoing a process of evolution, and changes occur. In this process, phraseological units also undergo changes related to their use, expansion and interpretation. One such change is called the terminologization of phraseological units.

N.N. Melex stated that, “the process of transition of the term into the universal vocabulary is characterized by phonetic, semantic, morphological, graphic, syntactic, pragmatic and psycholinguistic features along with the change of the meaning of the terminological unit” [Мелех 2004: 4-5].

According to A.D. Khayutin, linguistic terms “can be defined as words associated with a certain object of knowledge (conceptual or material object)...after that, they enter into a systematic connection with other similar words and together form a special terminological system organizes” [Хаяутин 1972: 16].

The terminological system is introduced into the language as a phenomenon that has a semiotic character in contrast to the natural language system, as well as a system of private and isolated language signs. A term is not considered an element of common language until its meaning is widely known. If the meaning expressed by the term goes beyond the scope of the system of special concepts, it becomes an element of the general language vocabulary and is included in the general language, but it still remains a term in the terminological system.

This position proves that, despite the difference between term and word described

above, they have a lot in common, basically, both term and word are units of the communicative system of language. It is not without reason that scientists start from the fact that a word (or a phrase) is the main conceptual element of language when defining a term.

The penetration of terminological expressions into the phraseological system of any language and, at the same time, the terminologization of phraseological units is one of the most interesting phenomena for modern linguistics. In this research, we consider the issue of terminologization of phraseological units, when they acquire additional meaning under the influence of certain factors and begin to function as superverbal terms in the language, that is, phraseological units. In addition, we analyze the process of transition of scientific phraseological units to terminology – in the phenomenon of terminologization. Before analyzing examples of the terminologization of these units, it is appropriate to give a definition of this process itself.

As we mentioned above, one of the most active ways of the emergence of terms is the semantic development of a common word, or in other words, terminologization process. This problem in linguistics has recently attracted the attention of Russian linguists such as S.V. Grinev, V.P. Danilenko, L.A. Kapanadze, F.P. Sorokoletov, V.A. Tatarinov, A.N. Shilovskiy, D.N. Shmelev, A.N. Shurygin [Гринев 1993; Даниленко 1971; Капанадзе 1999; Сороколетов 1981; Татаринов 1999; Шмелев 1969; Шурыгин 2005] and others, although there are already well-known opinions and considerations on this issue in the science, but its solution has not been found yet.

Russian linguist Yu.S. Sorokin, in his work “Язык науки и литературный язык”, compare the language of science and the language of literature and writes: “The language of science does not reflect the general laws of literary speech or is not accepted as different from them” [Сорокин 1972: 181]. Indeed, the terms are not only related to science, but also reflect the laws of our common speech, that is, they are closely related to each other. Thus, as we noted above,

terminology is a very influential layer of any natural language. Sources of terms are not only variable expressions, but also phraseological units.

V.M. Leychik in his article “Термины-фразаологизмы в ряду номинативных словосочетаний терминологического характера” [Лейчик 2003] developed various criteria for the differentiation of terms and phrases and put forward the actual problem of the transformation of commonly used phraseological units into terms.

In Russian linguistics, various definitions are given to the process of terminologization, in particular, “the state of changing the meaning of a certain phraseological unit from abstract to concrete” (Danilova, 1980), “the process that occurs in the semantic structure of the word” (Makeeva, 1990), “in the field of fixation (in dictionaries, references) is interpreted as a special process that takes place” (Shkatova, 1998). In other words, phraseological units break their connection with the system of phraseologisms, become a full-fledged member of the terminological system and form a unique terminological content, the etymology of which is observed in the denotative sense.

A.Yu. Fetisov defined terminologization as “the process of gradual change of the state of stability/instability, forming the basis of a metaphorical concept” [Фетисов 2000: 8].

Based on the above definitions, we can say that the terminologization of phraseological units is the process of acquiring a specific meaning of phraseological units related to the scope of a certain field of knowledge or activity. As a result of such a phenomenon, phraseological units are included in the vocabulary of a special language used in scientific, technical or professional fields.

Phraseological units can serve not only for the terminological system of business, economic, medical, military or legal terms, but also for the emergence of scientific terminological units.

For example, the phraseological unit *stalking horse* [Кунин 2005: 397] expresses the following meaning:

1) предлог, отговорка [этим. охот, заслонная лошадь];

2) подставное лицо, ширма”;

3) амер, полит, фиктивная кандидатура; кандидатура, выдвигаемая с целью раскола голосов сторонников другой партии.

In hunting terminology, this unit means a special technique when hunters hide behind a cardboard horse (horses) so as not to spook the prey ahead of time. When this unit was transposed into a non-terminological context, it developed a rethought meaning, meaning “pretext” or “screen” in order to hide true intentions or conceal the truth, in relation to a person, i.e., having a pronounced anthropocentric character.

But the process of rethinking did not end there, and over time, the phrase *stalking horse* acquired the meaning of “fictitious candidacy” in American political language:

A politician who tests the strength of a party's support for its leader by competing for the job of leading the party although they do not really intend to be elected. (Th. Dreiser, “A book about Myself”, Ch. X.)

Thus, we can state that during the phraseologization of the original terminological unit, the seme “to conceal, to deceive,” inherent in the term, was in a latent state. When this unit was placed in a terminological political context, the seme was the reason for the next rethinking and development of terminological meaning, different from the primary one, but undoubtedly genetically related to it.

Let us give examples of the use of this unit in its phraseological meaning and in the new terminological meaning.

Democracy has been used as a stalking horse for caucus rule [Кунин 2005: 398].

In this context, the terminology is used in the figurative meaning of “screen”, but in relation to democracy. That is, a semantic shift is planned for the unit to move into the category of political terms.

Indeed, phraseological units occupy an important place in the language and enrich its expressive possibilities. This, in turn, serves the correct and emotional expression of

thoughts and feelings. Terminologization of phraseological units is one of the important processes that allows adapting the language to the changing needs and requirements of society and professional activity. It contributes to the creation of a common language and ensures more effective communication within the professional community. Thus, understanding and studying the theoretical aspects of terminologization of phraseological units is an important task of linguists and specialists in various fields of knowledge.

In conclusion, it can be said that the terminologization of phraseological units is a complex process that includes adaptation of

expressions to new conditions of use, changes in their structure and semantics, as well as functional use in specialized texts. This process is an integral part of the development of language and its ability to adapt to various areas of human activity. Besides, terminologization of phraseological units is one of the multifaceted processes that affect the development of language and society as a whole. This process is related to sociolinguistic and linguistic changes and has practical applications in various fields of activity. Understanding and researching it allows for a deeper understanding and analysis of language phenomena, its impact on society.

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Sheraliyeva Sh. Ilmiy diskursda frazeologik birliklar terminologizatsiyasi. Mazkur tadqiqotdan ko'zlangan asosiy maqsad – ilmiy diskursda frazeologik birliklar terminologizatsiya muammolarini yoritishdan iborat. Ushbu mavzu bo'yicha bir qator ilmiy ishlar tadqiq qilindi. Mazkur masalaga turli olimlarning qarashlari misol tariqasida keltirilgan. Ilmiy diskursda frazeologik birliklarning terminologizatsiya muammosini o'rganish zamonaviy dunyoda dolzarb va muhim hisoblanadi, chunki frazeologik birliklar tilshunoslikda muhim rol o'ynaydi va har qanday tilning ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotimizning vazifalari sifatida esa frazeologiyada, xususan, terminologik frazeologizmlarda terminologizatsiya hodisasini yoritish tashkil etdi. Mazkur tadqiqot ishida qo'yilgan maqsadga erishish va belgilangan vazifalarni bajarishda quyidagi tilshunoslik va fanlararo tadqiqot metodlaridan foydalanildi: lisoniy tavsif metodi; oppozitsiyalar metodi; kommunikativ tilshunoslik metodlari, xususan, transformatsion metod; semantik metod.

Шералиева Ш. Терминологизации фразеологических единиц в научном дискурсе. Основной целью данного исследования является определить терминологизацию фразеологических единиц в научном дискурсе. На эту тему написано ряд научных работ. В качестве примера приведены взгляды разных ученых на эту концепцию. Исследование терминологизации фразеологических единиц в научном дискурсе актуально и важно в современном мире, поскольку фразеологизмы играют важную роль в языкознании и являются неотъемлемой частью любого языка. Задачей нашего исследования было выяснение явления терминологизации во фразеологии, в частности, в терминологических фразеологизмах. Для достижения цели и выполнения задач, поставленных в данной исследовательской работе, были использованы следующие лингвистические и междисциплинарные методы исследования: метод лингвистического описания; метод оппозиций; методы коммуникативной лингвистики, в частности трансформационный метод; семантический метод.